

CYCLOPES - Fighting Cybercrime – Law Enforcement Practitioners’ Network

Deliverable 7.3 Actionable Ethics and Legal Guidance Documents

Public

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Introduction

In what comes to ethics, the question is often much more important than the answer. The reason for this is that ethics, ethical questions, and puzzles, become tangible only when someone first thinks of them, and then raises their voice and asks the question. Asking is thus the starting point for the quest toward a satisfied solution. So, for this I thank you, that you have opened this deliverable, since obviously you are either interested in ethical questions, or you have a question that you are seeking an answer – therefore making ethics alive and tangible.

This document aims to give actionable guidance, i.e. give advice and information on some key ethical issues that are not covered in other ethical deliverables of our project, for example on consent, consent forms, non-EU members etc. Therefore, first, this document will present the so-called Data Protection Officers (DPOs) and how they can be of help in CYCLOPES. Then after, the Ethical Self-Assessment will be introduced. This is a tool to assess the work we are doing, and making sure that critical ethical issues are taken into account. The self-assessment is online, and done in EUSurvey tool, so when filling it out, this will create simultaneously a paper trail of the assessment that can be used in reporting the ethical work of CYCLOPES. The third topic of this deliverable is data breach. Thus, in this deliverable you may find tangible guidance on what to do if and when there is a possible data breach. The fourth presented in this deliverable is the concept of whistleblower, i.e. reporting of potential misconduct and violations. Lastly, questions related with cybersecurity, more precisely, risk of a cyberattack will be addressed.

Data Protection Officers

A Data Protection Officer is a role in (many) organisations required by law (Regulation (EU) 2018/1725). The DPO's aims and objectives are to ensure that her organisation processes the personal data of its staff, customers, providers or any other individuals (also referred to as data subjects) in compliance with the applicable data protection rules.

The General Data Protection Regulation (Art 39) defines the tasks of the DPO, too. According to the legislation, DPO shall have at least the following tasks:

- 1) to inform and advise the controller or the processor and the employees who carry out processing of their obligations pursuant to this Regulation and to other Union or Member State data protection provisions;
- 2) to monitor compliance with this Regulation, with other Union or Member State data protection provisions and with the policies of the controller or processor in relation to the protection of personal data, including the assignment of responsibilities, awareness-raising and training of staff involved in processing operations, and the related audits;
- 3) to provide advice where requested as regards the data protection impact assessment and monitor its performance pursuant to Article 35;
- 4) to cooperate with the supervisory authority;
- 5) to act as the contact point for the supervisory authority on issues relating to processing, including the prior consultation referred to in Article 36, and
- 6) to consult, where appropriate, with regard to any other matter.

Therefore, in most of the CYCLOPES organisations, the DPO is the person who knows to answer to the various questions on data protection and GDPR. Thus, it is most welcomed to be informed of the DPOs in each of the member organisations: he or she is to help you in your work in CYCLOPES too. Especially important is for those partners who are collecting and/or processing of personal data. Then, for example, the DPOs contact details should be made available to data subjects.

In case your organisation does not have one a detailed data protection policy for the CYCLOPES, including among others, the procedures for data collection, storage, protection, retention, and destruction, needs to be drafted and followed.

More information can be found from the Commission's web sites, See for example: https://edps.europa.eu/data-protection/data-protection/reference-library/data-protection-officer-dpo_en

Ethical Self-Assessment

The Ethical Self-Assessment of CYCLOPES can be found online at:

https://ec.europa.eu/eusurvey/runner/CYCLOPES_Ethical-self-assessment

The assessment is done with the EUSurvey tool¹, and can be filled in online using the above address.

This evaluation form is based on the ethics self-assessment of Horizon 2020 projects. The self-assessment should be completed for all deliverables / research activities / development tasks by the responsible partner of the activity.

First will be asked information on the research and/or other activity, e.g. the related Work Package, the deliverable etc. Then, details of the person and organisation filling the assessment. CYCLOPES is not interested in the personal details *per se*, but in case there is need for elaborating some answers, we need the information. Therefore, we are asking for consent for giving personal information, and we are providing related information sheet.

Then after, the actual ethical questions will be answered. The first in on human embryos/foetuses, and simply asks: “Does your research involve Human Embryonic Stem Cells (HESCs)?” This is followed by Yes/No choices. And if you indeed are involved with HESCs and answer “Yes”, then a follow up question will emerge (Please specify / elaborate) together with guidance to contact the Ethical Manager of the project, and to wait further instructions before starting the R&D work.

Similar questions follows then on:

- human participation,
- use of human cells or tissues,
- collection of personal data and/or processing,
- tracking or observation of participants,
- the use of informed consent forms,
- involvement of animals,
- involvement of non-EU countries,
- imports of any material from non-EU countries into the EU,
- possible harm to the environment, animals or plants, or humans,
- possible dual use,
- possible misuse, and of course,
- any other ethical issues.

The EUSurvey will then store the answers into a secure server, and the answers can be uploaded e.g. in Excel-format to be further analysed and modified. One can also save a copy for own use, for example, if when answering the respondent realises that an ethical issue has been neglected and corrective actions are needed.

¹ More about EUSurvey, please visit <https://ec.europa.eu/eusurvey/>

The self-assessments in EUSurvey will also help the ethical management greatly having an automated so-called paper trail of the assessments. These can be included in the reporting to Commission.

Below is an extract from the EUSurvey webpage:

1. HUMAN EMBRYOS/FOETUSES

* Does your research involve Human Embryonic Stem Cells (HESCs)?

- Yes
 No

2. HUMANS

* Does your research involve Human Participants?

- Yes
 No

Activities to be taken:

The researchers should provide:

An **Informed consent forms** with an **information sheet** specifying the nature of the research.

Thus, please reply to the follow-up questions:

Was Informed consent forms together with an information sheet provided?

- Yes
 No

Was there participants from outside the project consortium?

- Yes
 No

Please specify/elaborate (if needed):

3. HUMAN CELLS / TISSUES

* Does your research involve human cells or tissues (other than from Human Embryos/ Foetuses, i.e. Question #1 above)?

- Yes
 No
-

Data Breach

“What to do, when things go wrong?” – In the field of Compliance this is most likely the second most important question – second only to the question how to prevent things from going wrong.² Fortunately, CYCLOPES, unlike other research projects, is not handling personal data on a large scale. Therefore, at least data breach incidents involving masses of personal data are less likely.

What happens during a “data breach”?

The term “data breach” is usually used to describe unauthorised access to – and in many cases subsequent release of confidential information.³ Offenders have developed sophisticated methods to carry out their attacks.⁴ Among the largest data breach incidents were the Yahoo incident in 2013 that involved around 3 billion accounts⁵ and the LinkedIn incident in 2021, that affected 700 million users.⁶ It is important to highlight that data breaches are not limited to large enterprises – potentially research projects, Law Enforcement Agencies and research institutions could be targeted as well.

How to respond?

The following chapter provides a basic guidance with regard to this topic. It is based on 6 principles:

1) Know your organization’s emergency plans

This document neither can nor is intended to substitute your organisation’s emergency plans for data breach management or violations of ethics standards. Not the least because despite intense European harmonisation in the field of data protection⁷ there are national specifications, that your organisation might need to take into account. As a consequence, the first action item for any Consortium Member in terms of incident management is to collect your organisation’s emergency plans, study the processes described there and apply them in case of an incident. In case you do not have such internal documents, the Data Protection Officer (DPO) or the Compliance Officer (CO) are institutions that could and should be consulted.

2) In absence of a plan: Develop a plan

If you find out that your organisation does not have an emergency plan in place, either initiate the development or a create such a plan, at least for the team involved in any activities concerning the CYCLOPES project. There are various guides available that support the

² For additional information about compliance see: *Banks/Banks*, Corporate Legal Compliance Handbook, 2021; *Fox*, The Compliance Handbook A Guide to Operationalizing Your Compliance Program, 2018.

³ For more information on data breaches see for example: *Fowler*, Data Breach Preparation and Response, 2016.

⁴ For details see: ForgeRock 2021 Breach Report.

⁵ See: *Stempel/Finkle*, Yahoo says all three billion accounts hacked in 2013 data theft, Reuters, 03.10.2017; *Perloth*, All 3 Billion Yahoo Accounts Were Affected by 2013 Attack, NYT, 03.10.2017.

⁶ See: *Morris*, Massiv data leak exposes 700 million Linkeln users’ information, Fortune, 30.06.2021; *Marks*, A LinkedIn Breach Exposes 92% Of Users, Forbes, 05.06.2021.

⁷ The most well-known harmonization approach is the General Data Protection Regulation (GDPR). Regarding the GDPR see for example: *Feiler/Forgo/Weigl*, The EU Data Protection Regulation (GDPR), A Commentary, 2018; *Voigt/von dem Bussche*, The EU General Data Protection Regulation, A Practical Guide, 2017.

development of such plans.⁸ However, it is important to point out that it is favourable when your entire organisation develops such plan instead of a research team alone. Especially because there are significant legal aspects (such as notification requirements) that need to be taken into account.

3) Prepare for a true crisis

It is one thing to studying and developing an emergency plan – preparing for a real incident is different. Real incidents usually go along with stress. Realistic exercises (“wargaming”) can help to prepare for incidents.⁹ This does not necessarily require extensive preparation. Running such exercises at least once with the people involved in the CYCLOPES project and in charge of incident management can help to ensure a basic level of realistic preparation.

4) See something – say something

An incident does not necessarily need to lead to severe consequences if the right response is applied immediately. Therefore, it is important that the emergency plan is triggered right away as soon as there are any reliable indications for a possible incident (e.g. a data breach).

Taking into account that a possible incident could potentially not only affect your organisation, it is of great relevance that you reach out to the Project Management right away. Here are the relevant contact details:

Project Coordinator:

Rashel Talukder, Stowarzyszenie Polska Platforma Bezpieczeństwa Wewnętrznego, Ul. Slowackiego 17/11, 60-822 Poznan, Poland, phone: +48 61 663 02 21

5) Prepare for questions

If there was an incident, the people potentially affected by it are likely to have questions. Being able to respond in time to legitimate questions can be an essential component of a successful incident management. Preparing transparent information on what happened, what the next steps are and what affected people can do now, is a starting point. As relevant as this information itself is to ensure that there are resources available to respond to legitimate requests.

6) Follow the law

As indicated above, especially data protection is heavily regulated. If an incident is related to personal data, it is important to be aware that the EU General Data Protection Regulation applies and its minimum requirements regarding incident management have to be met. The mandatory incident management procedure might include notification requirements (Art. 33 and 34 GDPR) and the right of all affected individuals (data subjects) to request various information regarding their personal data (Art. 15 GDPR).

⁸ See for example: Incident Response Reference Guide, First aid tips and preparation guidance to limit damage and protect you mission, available at: <https://info.microsoft.com/rs/157-GQE-382/images/EN-US-CNTNT-emergency-doc-digital.pdf>,

⁹ Regarding wargaming in general see: *Herman/Frost/ Kurz, Wargaming for Leaders. 2009; Sabin, Simulating War, 2012.* Regarding the use of wargaming for crisis preparation see: *Gercke, How Can management and Supervisory Boards Members become more involved in Cybersecurity, published in in Abbolhassan, Security, 2016.*

Resources

If you are looking for additional information, there are various publications referenced in this document, that you could consult. The European Commission has set up a website that also provides additional information:

https://ec.europa.eu/info/law/law-topic/data-protection/reform/rules-business-and-organisations/obligations/what-data-breach-and-what-do-we-have-to-do-in-case-of-a-data-breach_en

The European Commission also provides guidance for individuals that are affected by a data breach:

https://ec.europa.eu/info/law/law-topic/data-protection/reform/rights-citizens/redress/what-should-i-do-if-i-think-my-personal-data-protection-rights-have-not-been-respected_en

Whistleblower

The following chapter provides guidance to the topic of whistleblowers. The EU legislator has addressed the topic in the recent Directive (EU) 2019/1937 of the European Parliament and of the Council of 23 October 2019 on the protection of persons who report breaches of Union law. The Directive has to be implemented by the EU Member States by 17th December 2021. While the implementation into national law may vary to a certain extent among Member States, the Directive nevertheless harmonizes the legislation in this area throughout the European Union.

What is whistleblowing?

Since the revelations of Edward Snowden and Wikileaks founder Julian Assange, the term "whistleblower" has become known to most people. The subject of whistleblowing is increasingly part of media reporting. For many people, whistleblowers are considered heroes because it seems that informing society is more important to them than the fear of negative consequences for their personal situation. Cases of whistleblowing can harbour different risks or consequences for employees, companies or entire countries.¹⁰

For example, Daniel Ellsberg, who passed on secret information to the New York Times in 1971 related to the Vietnam War, is still one of the best-known whistleblowers today. By leaking the "Pentagon Papers" he drew attention to the grievances concerning the Vietnam War which the US government had deceived the American people about. Ellsberg had worked as a military expert for the government. By passing on the explosive documents, he faced 115 years imprisonment for espionage.

A more recent example is the case of the US company "Theranos", founded by Elisabeth Holmes in 2003. "Theranos" raised more than 700 million USD from venture capitalists and private investors, resulting in a US \$9 billion valuation at its peak in 2013 and 2014.¹¹ The company was about developing a machine called "Edison" that was intended be able to perform more than 200 different blood tests with only a few drops of blood. However, it turned out that "Edison" could only reliably carry out one single test.¹² An investigative reporter discovered in 2015 that the company had secretly used Siemens analysis devices behind the curtain. Holmes denied the allegations before several employees of "Theranos" decided to blow the whistle and and reveal the truth to the public. The trial against Elizabeth Holmes just began in September 2021 and her whistleblowing employees will testify as witnesses in order to prove that Holmes knew, the blood test machine was unusable. If convicted, she will face many years in prison.

Whistleblowing is primarily a matter of drawing attention to misconduct, illegal machinations or unethical behaviour that is actually not intended for the public's eyes. Whistleblowers often risk a lot for this. In some countries, including Germany, a lack of sufficient protection for whistleblowers against dismissal or other personal disadvantages was lamented in the past.

¹⁰ *Böhmer/Bolzen/Flade/Graw/Hackensberger/Kurz*, Wird die Welt wirklich besser durch Leaks?, Welt, 10.05.2016. *Beuth*, Hat Snowden die Welt verändert? Zeit Online, 5.06.2014.

<https://www.zeit.de/digital/datenschutz/2014-05/ein-jahr-snowden-bilanz>

¹¹ <https://en.wikipedia.org/wiki/Theranos>.

¹² *Pflanzer*, Theranos is only using its revolutionary blood testing technology on one of its 200+ test, Business Insider, 16.10.2015.

General Remark

This document neither can and nor is intended to substitute your organisation's emergency plans for whistleblower management or violations of ethics standards. Not the least there are national specifications, that your organisation might need to take into account. As a consequence, the first action item for any Consortium Member for complaint management is to collect information regarding the allegations. Despite this, here is some practical guidance that can be extracted from the EU-Directive on how to deal with whistleblowing:

What to do when you believe a member of your organisation/team working in the course of CYCLOPES is a whistleblower?

Any report about potential misconduct is welcome. *First*, it should be examined if the complaint he or she raises is true or not. *Second*, it should be determined if the complaint relates to a serious fault. It may be advisable to suspend the related process or activities pending the outcome of the investigation. Please keep in mind that this could affect the CYCLOPES project in general or at least other contributing Consortium Members, so they might have to be notified about the delay as well as the Project Management for CYCLOPES.

A confirmation of receipt should be sent to the potential whistleblower within seven days of receiving his/her report. After three months at the latest, the whistleblower should receive feedback on what follow-up measures have been taken or are still planned.¹³

Next, it has to be figured out whether the complaint is a personal complaint or whistleblowing within the context of the EU-Directive.¹⁴ If whistleblowing is confirmed, the whistleblower may be entitled to legal protection under the EU-Directive¹⁵ or the protection plan (whistleblower-system) of your organisation and the national law.

If the investigations reveal that the allegations are true, it is advisable to deal with the facts as openly and transparently as possible to demonstrate that your organisation takes the concerns seriously and exercises disciplinary measures against misconducting perpetrators.

Prepare for questions: If whistleblowing has occurred, the people affected by the misconduct are likely to have questions. Being able to respond in time to legitimate questions can be an

¹³ See: Art. 9 (b) and (f) of the Directive (EU) 2019/1937 of 23 October 2019 of the European Parliament and of the Council on the protection of persons who report breaches of Union law: (b) acknowledgment of receipt of the report to the reporting person within seven days of that receipt; (f) a reasonable timeframe to provide feedback, not exceeding three months from the acknowledgment of receipt or, if no acknowledgement was sent to the reporting person, three months from the expiry of the seven-day period after the report was made.

¹⁴ See: Art. 5 (1), (2) of of the Directive (EU) 2019/1937 of 23 October 2019 of the European Parliament and of the Council on the protection of persons who report breaches of Union law: Definitions: For the purposes of this Directive, the following definitions apply:(1) 'breaches' means acts or omissions that:(i) are unlawful and relate to the Union acts and areas falling within the material scope referred to in Article 2; or(ii) defeat the object or the purpose of the rules in the Union acts and areas falling within the material scope referred to in Article 2;(2) 'information on breaches' means information, including reasonable suspicions, about actual or potential breaches, which occurred or are very likely to occur in the organisation in which the reporting person works or has worked or in another organisation with which the reporting person is or was in contact through his or her work, and about attempts to conceal such breaches.

¹⁵ See. Art. 6 of the Directive (EU) 2019/1937 of 23 October 2019 of the European Parliament and of the Council on the protection of persons who report breaches of Union law: Conditions for protection of reporting persons.

essential component of a successful whistleblowing management. Preparing transparent information on what happened, what the next steps are and what affected people can do now, is a starting point.

Is there a way to “prevent” negative consequences of whistleblowing?

It seems contradictory, but the best way to prevent negative consequences of whistleblowing is to develop an internal whistleblower-system. Building a whistleblower-system is one of the central obligations of the EU-Directive for companies and legal entities with more than 50 employees. They are required to implement suitable internal procedures for receiving reports and setting up processes for proper follow-up measures. Here are some requirements of an internal whistleblower-system:

- ensure an open corporate structure of your organisation;
- define processes for investigating grievances;
- convince your employees that uncovering grievances is in the organisations` interest;
- create easily accessible and anonymised reporting channels in different languages;¹⁶
- develop an escalation plan;
- observe national law and in particular the GDPR.

After the Whistleblowing

If the whistleblower leaked sensitive information externally instead of filing the suspected misconduct internally, the organisation’s reputation and indirectly by extension the reputation of CYCLOPES and its Consortium Members could be on the line. This may influence the relationship between the organisation and external partners (e.g. CYCLOPES Consortium Members) in a negative way, especially if the allegations of a breach in the organisation turn out to be true. Work actively to clear up the allegations. In order to avoid a serious crisis, it is important to have an emergency plan in the event that grievances are exposed externally. This plan should in particular contain standards of external communication.

Summary

The EU-Directive ensures that whistleblowers do not have to fear any negative consequences. This guideline is intended to encourage the reporting of potential misconduct and violations in companies and organisations, even in authorities. It is intended to prevent and detect procurement-related fraud and corruption in the context of the implementation of the Union budget, but also to tackle insufficient enforcement of rules on public procurement by national contracting authorities and contracting entities in relation to the execution of works, the supply of products or the provision of services.¹⁷ The guideline therefore also applies in particular to projects carried out by the EU. It is, therefore, also important in this project to take into account the legislation in this area and to create the conditions that avoid external whistleblowing in the best case.

¹⁶ See: Art. 9 of the Directive (EU) 2019/1937 of 23 October 2019 of the European Parliament and of the Council on the protection of persons who report breaches of Union law: “channels for receiving the reports which are designed, established and operated in a secure manner that ensures that the confidentiality of the identity of the reporting person and any third party mentioned in the report is protected, and prevents access thereto by non-authorised staff members”

¹⁷ See: Directive (EU) 2019/1937 of 23 October 2019 of the European Parliament and of the Council on the protection of persons who report breaches of Union law, Introduction (6).

Cybersecurity

Whereas “data breach” deals with unauthorised access to confidential information (see above), cybersecurity addresses the wider and equally imminent risk of a cyberattack. The risk of cyberattacks on organisations has been on the rise for the last decade, but has significantly increased with the COVID-19 pandemic due to the fast shift to telework which has provided new attack vectors for gaining access to an organisation’s IT-infrastructure.¹⁸ The ability to manage the risk of cybersecurity incidents in a preventative manner has, therefore, become even more imminent. The management of an organisation’s cybersecurity requires not only specific technical protection measures but also continuous training of the people involved.

Aim

The proper management of cybersecurity is aimed at achieving and demonstrating an appropriate level of cyber-resilience in compliance with legal and ethical requirements. This document neither can nor is intended to substitute your organisation’s existing plans for cybersecurity management or violations of ethics standards. Despite intense European harmonisation in the field of cybersecurity requirements, there are national specifications that your organisation has to take into account.

At EU level, the NIS Directive¹⁹ addresses cybersecurity and was aimed at increasing Member State capacities in this field by having competent authorities designated for monitoring compliance with the NIS Directive as well as central national contact points as liaison offices for supranational cooperation and set up Computer Security Incident Response Teams (CSIRTs), on the one hand, and establish a mandatory set of minimum cybersecurity requirements for “essential services” and “digital services”, on the other. In December 2020, the European Commission presented a Proposal for a future NIS 2 Directive.²⁰ The proposed NIS 2 Directive distinguishes only between “essential” and “important” facilities based on their degree of criticality of the sector.²¹ This new distinction significantly extends the number of entities having to comply with the mandatory cybersecurity requirements and includes all medium-sized and large enterprises in the critical sectors.²² The catalogue of mandatory cybersecurity measures includes risk analysis and security concepts, prevention of security incidents and crisis management,²³ and the reporting obligations of entities are specified in terms of procedure, content and timeframe for reporting a cybersecurity incident.²⁴

How to prepare?

While the European Commission’s Proposal for a NIS 2 Directive shows that the legal requirements for cybersecurity compliance are soon to change, the NIS Directive is long in

¹⁸ Europol, Internet Organised Crime Threat Assessment (IOCTA) 2020, p. 25.

¹⁹ Directive (EU) 2016/1148 of the European Parliament and of the Council of 6 July 2016 concerning measures for a high common level of security of network and information systems across the Union (NIS Directive), OJ L 194, 19 July 2016, pp. 1–30.

²⁰ European Commission, Proposal for a Directive of the European Parliament and of the Council on measures for a high common level of cybersecurity across the Union, repealing Directive (EU) 2016/1148, COM(2020) 823 final, 16 December 2020 (NIS 2 Directive), available at: https://ec.europa.eu/newsroom/dae/document.cfm?doc_id=72166.

²¹ European Commission, Proposal for a NIS 2 Directive (note 19), Recital 11.

²² European Commission, Proposal for a NIS 2 Directive (note 19), Art. 2(1).

²³ European Commission, Proposal for a NIS 2 Directive (note 19), Art. 18.

²⁴ European Commission, Proposal for a NIS 2 Directive (note 19), Art. 20.

force and implemented as well as supplemented by national cybersecurity law. As a consequence, the first action item for any Consortium Member in terms of incident management is to collect your organisation's cybersecurity management plan, study the processes described there and apply them in case of an incident. In case you do not have such internal documents at hand, the Cybersecurity Officer (DPO) or the Compliance Officer (CO) are institutions that could and should be consulted.

Plan

While the minimum cybersecurity requirements based on the NIS Directive are mandatory only for "essential services" and "digital services", they provide a good starting point for any organisation to improve its cybersecurity risk management and incident response. Regardless of size, degree of cyber security risk, or cyber security sophistication, the NIS Directive provides helpful principles and best practices for improving cybersecurity and resilience in any organisation. Please bear in mind that your organisation also conducts other activities than those in the course of the CYCLOPES project. Therefore, your organisation might have to consider some risks, threats and vulnerabilities as well which are unique to your organisation. The measures highlighted here are very general and intended to show a direction of how to increase the level of cybersecurity for network and information systems.

Technical and Organisational Measures (TOMs)

The technical and organisational measures need to allow for managing the risks posed to the cybersecurity of the network and information systems used in your organisation's operations and for minimising the impact of cybersecurity incidents affecting those systems. The TOMs could be designed to:

- enable your organisation to accurately describe your organisation's current cybersecurity status, at all times;
- provide an outcome-focused approach of the cybersecurity principles for network and information systems;
- be compatible with and complement your organisation's existing Risk Management, Standards and Cybersecurity Programs;
- enable the identification of effective cybersecurity improvement activities.²⁵

Five Key Aspects

For a high-level view of your organisation's management of cybersecurity risks, the following five core aspects seem a good starting point:

1) Identify

Your organisation could develop an organisational understanding, structures, policies and processes to manage cybersecurity risk to the network and information systems of your organisation's essential services, assets, data, and capabilities.²⁶

²⁵ See: National Cyber Security Centre (NCSC), NIS Compliance Guidelines for Operators of Essential Service (OES), August 2019, p. 8, available at: https://www.ncsc.gov.ie/pdfs/NIS_Compliance_Security_Guidelines_for_OES.pdf.

²⁶ See: National Cyber Security Centre (NCSC), NIS Compliance Guidelines for Operators of Essential Service (OES), August 2019, p. 9, available at: https://www.ncsc.gov.ie/pdfs/NIS_Compliance_Security_Guidelines_for_OES.pdf.

2) Protect

Your organisation could aim for the capability to protect the elements deemed as critical (data, personnel, devices, systems, facilities) to your organisation's activities based on the people, processes and technologies in place. Critical to protecting your organisation seems the premise of developing and implementing appropriate and proportionate security measures that allow the delivery and protection of your organisation's essential services and systems. This could include:²⁷

- **Identity Management, Authentication and Access Control:**

Access to assets and associated facilities is limited to authorised users, processes, and devices, consistent with the principle of least privilege and is managed consistent with the assessed risk.

- **Awareness and Training:**

Personnel and partners are provided cybersecurity awareness education and are trained to perform their cybersecurity-related duties and responsibilities consistent with related documented policies, procedures, and agreements.

- **Data Security:**

Information and records (data) are managed consistent with the risk strategy to protect the confidentiality, integrity, and availability of information and systems.

- **Service Protection Policies, Processes and Procedures:**

Definition, communication and documentation of appropriate policies, processes and procedures that direct the overall organisational approach to securing systems and data that support delivery of essential services.

- **Maintenance:**

Maintenance and repairs of critical system components are performed consistent with policies and procedures.

- **Protective Technology:**

Technical security solutions are managed to ensure the security and resilience of systems and assets, consistent with related policies, procedures, and agreements.

3) Detect

Your organisation could aim to develop and implement appropriate capabilities to identify, detect and defend against the occurrence of a cybersecurity incident that could affect essential services; involving:²⁸

- Detection of anomalies and incidents,
- Continuous monitoring of cybersecurity, and
- Documentation of periodic and effective detection processes.

²⁷ See: National Cyber Security Centre (NCSC), NIS Compliance Guidelines for Operators of Essential Service (OES), August 2019, p. 10-11, available at: https://www.ncsc.gov.ie/pdfs/NIS_Compliance_Security_Guidelines_for_OES.pdf.

²⁸ See: National Cyber Security Centre (NCSC), NIS Compliance Guidelines for Operators of Essential Service (OES), August 2019, p. 11, available at: https://www.ncsc.gov.ie/pdfs/NIS_Compliance_Security_Guidelines_for_OES.pdf.

4) Respond

The response of your organisation could aim to support the ability to contain and minimise the impact of a potential cybersecurity incident which would require planning of appropriate response processes and procedures (including mitigation measures) as well as communication. In case the cybersecurity incident has the potential of affecting other organisations as well, then it is vital that you reach out immediately to the Project Management for the CYCLOPES project.²⁹

5) Recover

Develop and implement the appropriate capabilities, prioritised through the organisations risk management process, to restore the capabilities of essential services that were affected through a cybersecurity incident.

Prepare for questions

If there was a cybersecurity incident, the people potentially affected by it are likely to have questions. Being able to respond in time to legitimate questions can be an essential component of a successful incident management. Preparing transparent information on what happened, what the next steps are and what affected people can do now, is a starting point. As relevant as this information itself is to ensure that there are resources available to respond to legitimate requests.

Follow the law

Cybersecurity is increasingly regulated. It is crucial to know whether the activities of your organisation are regulated by the NIS Directive and its national implementation as well as by additional Member State law on cybersecurity. If a cybersecurity incident affects personal data, it is important to realise, that the EU General Data Protection Regulation applies independently and in addition to any cybersecurity law, so that the GDPR's minimum incident management requirements have to be met which might include notification requirements (Art. 33 and 34 GDPR) and the right of all affected individuals (data subjects) to request various information regarding their personal data (Art. 15 GDPR).

²⁹ See: National Cyber Security Centre (NCSC), NIS Compliance Guidelines for Operators of Essential Service (OES), August 2019, p. 12, available at: https://www.ncsc.gov.ie/pdfs/NIS_Compliance_Security_Guidelines_for_OES.pdf.

Conclusions

The aim of this deliverable is to give tangible guidance on ethical issues to the CYCLOPES consortium. It does so by highlighting the existing resources that many of the partner organisations already have, i.e. the Data Protection Officers. These are the persons whom to contact in each organisation if there are questions on GDPR compliance, for example. The second tangible ethical guidance comes in the form of Ethical Self-Assessment that is to be done. The assessment is in an online form, so that one can easily assess the ethicalness of his or her work, but also get information on what to do if ethical issues are raised. The third issue brought to the attention of the consortium is information on what to do in cases of data breach. The fourth guidance is knowledge on the concept of whistleblowing, and the final paragraph deals with cybersecurity and cyberattacks. Together these five aspects (not forgetting the other ethics deliverables of CYCLOPES) form an ensemble of ethical guidance that should help the member organisations to avoid ethical pitfalls. Naturally, the Ethical Manager and the whole management is to assist if any issues occur.